

doi 10.5281/zenodo.10217078

Vol. 06 Issue 11 Nov - 2023

Manuscript ID: #01142

PRINCIPALS' UTILIZATION OF COMMITTEE SYSTEM AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS' JOB EFFECTIVENESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

Prof. Perpetua Okorji & Ugochukwu Stephen Onedigbo

Dept. of Educational Management and Policy Faculty of Education, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka

ABSTRACT

The study investigated principals' utilization of committee system as predictors of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by three research questions and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 5,286 teachers (1,872 males and 3,124 females) in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for this study consisted of 529 teachers (187 males and 342 females) drawn using proportionate stratified sampling technique. A researcher-developed questionnaires titled "Principals' Utilization of Committee System Questionnaire (PUCSQ)" and "Teachers' Job Effectiveness Scale (TJES)" were used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from the Department of Educational Foundations, NnamdiAzikiwe University. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistency of the instruments which yielded overall coefficients of 0.78 and 0.81 for PUCSQ and TJES respectively. The researcher, together with five research assistants, collected data for the study using the direct approach method and 98% return was recorded. Simple regression was used for data analysis. The findings of the study revealed among others that principals' utilization of committee system is a moderate predictor of male teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also found that principals' utilization of committee system is a strong predictor of female teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, principals' utilization of committee system is strong predictor of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that principals should ensure fairness in gender representation in composing committee system to facilitate the job effectiveness of male and female teachers.

KEYWORDS:

Principals, Utilization, Committee System, Teachers, Job Effectiveness

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

Introduction

Education is an indispensable instrument for equipping individuals with the requisite skills and sound knowledge for the social, economic, scientific and technological advancement of the nation. It also enables individuals to develop the right attitudes, desirable behaviours and values which make them responsible members of society. Education takes place at basic, secondary and tertiary levels in almost all nations worldwide, Nigeria inclusive. The intermediate level in Nigeria is secondary education.

Secondary education, which takes place after primary education, is geared toward training, educating and helping the learners to develop the right attitude and skills for useful living in the society. It absorbs the products of primary schools and prepares them for tertiary institutions of learning. Okorji and Njoku (2020) asserted that secondary education which is the form of education that students receive after primary school has the unique and pivotal functions of preparing them for higher education and providing middle-level manpower for the development of the society. Similar to this, Unachukwu and Nwanga (2021) opined that secondary education, which serves as an intermediate between primary and tertiary levels of education, is designed to ensure the preparedness of individuals for further studies, self-reliance, active participation in societal affairs and meaningful contribution to the development of the society. The attainment of the objectives of secondary education to some extent depends on the principal who is in charge of the daily operations of the school.

The principal is the chief executive officer who oversees and controls the day-to-day activities of secondary school to achieve set educational goals. According to Edomwande and Anakah (2020), principal is the one who is responsible for the management, day-to-day operations and business of a secondary school. It is the duty of the principal to organize, supervise and oversee activities of staff to ensure smooth functioning of the school. Nwangwa and Barrah (2021) defined principal as the chief executive officer of a secondary school who performs administrative roles of planning, organizing, controlling and coordinating daily activities. The principal is responsible for coordinating, managing school resources and other numerous administrative tasks in a secondary school. Nnebedum, Akinfolarin and Obuegbe (2018) noted that the numerous administrative tasks of principals call for utilization of committee as a means of delegating responsibilities and authority to competent members of staff in the school.

Committee is the act of bringing individuals together as group to perform certain duties in an organization. Ogunode and Mcbrown (2022) defined committee system as the approach of constituting a group of people for a purpose of carrying out special assignments that are keys to the development of the institutions. The committee system enhances the participation of members of staff in running the affairs of the school. Jaiyeoba and Ojewumi (2022) pointed out that committee system, when used in secondary school, is expected to enhance administrative effectiveness and maintain democratic procedures for representation of views set out in the school system. Jaiyeoba and Ojewumi added that utilization of committee system may promote communication and acceptance of decision reached in the school. The committee system brings group of individuals to share ideas and work together to effectively perform task assigned to them. Contextually, committee system is act of constituting a group of people from a larger one to deliberate, investigate, recommend and take actions on a specific task.

The committee system exists in secondary schools to perform some specific functions. Jaiyeoba and Ojewumi(2022) identified committees normally constituted in schools as follows: disciplinary committee, examination committee, staff welfare committee and instructional supervision committee. Similarly, Nnebedum, Oshia, Nwanne and Chinagorom (2022) identified the various

committees that exist in secondary schools to include: disciplinary committee, health committee, planning committee, sport committee and staff welfare committee among others. The interest of this study is all the committees such as planning committee, disciplinary committee, examination committee, staff welfare committee, sport committee and instructional supervision committee which are constituted in secondary schools to contribute towards achieving predetermined objectives.

The existing committees in secondary schools perform various functions. Jaiyeoba and Ojewumi (2022) pointed out that the staff welfare committee is constituted to plan and organize programmes that are geared towards meeting the physical, social and psychologically well-being of staffs in the school. Welfare committee makes suggestions for creating favorable working environment which boost the morale of teachers in discharging their duties. Planning committee plan and develop curricular and co-curricular programmes in secondary schools. Nnebedum et al. (2018) sports committee Sports is set up for planning, organizing, controlling and promoting sporting activities in the school. Sports committee organizes activities such as football, basket ball, volley ball, track events and field events to improve the physical fitness of students in secondary schools. School disciplinary committee is a body constituted to maintain calm and peaceful academic atmosphere in learning institution. Nnebedum et al. (2018) noted that disciplinary committee is a body constituted for planning and taking necessary actions to ensure conformity with the established standards, rules and regulations governing an institution. Examination committee prepare timetable for examination, schedule invigilators and determine venues for the examination. Health committee is the body saddled with task of promoting the physical fitness and mental wellness of personnel in an organization. Morrison et al. (2020) noted that the health committee is responsible for increasing hygienic awareness, procuring of medical equipment and improving cleanliness of the physical environment, monitoring and maintaining regular medical care administer to personnel. The teachers who receive medical services could be physically fit to executive their duties to bring about improvement on their job effectiveness.

Teachers' job effectiveness is the act of meeting the expected standard in executing academic tasks in the school. Onyali, Nnebedum and Ejese (2020) defined teachers' effectiveness as the ability of teachers to utilize their skills and competencies to enhance attainment of the predetermined learning objectives. Teachers' job effectiveness is the ability to be successful in attaining desirable results in a given tasks. Teachers' job effectiveness is the act of maximizing the available resources to successfully discharge one's duties. Contextually, teachers' effectiveness is the degree to which members of teaching staff perform their instructional duties to improve students' academic performance and achieve set educational goals of equipping skills with useful skills and preparing them for further studies.

The teachers' effectiveness could be assessed through their teaching activities. Nwachukwu and Emunemu (2021) pointed out that teachers' job effectiveness is measured by their students' academic performance in examinations, punctuality at school and class, commitment to work, giving extra lessons to students and contribution to the progress of the school through participation in co-curricular activities such as sports, students' discipline and committee assignments as may be given by the principal. Similarly, Onyali, Nnebedum and Ejese (2020) noted that effective teachers have thorough understanding and knowledge of the subjects they teach and pedagogical methods for teaching those subjects to students, organize and manage classroom to promote teaching and learning, exhibit high level of proficiency in verbal and written communication, and respond to students' errors in a positive manner in order to enhance the attainment of the predetermined goals and objectives of the school. On the other hand, the indicators of teachers' job ineffectiveness as highlighted by Arop, Owan and Ekpang (2018) are absenteeism, poor lesson note preparation, lateness, indecent dressing,

being reluctant or lazy in carrying out assigned duties. Okogbaa and Igbogi (2019) noted that teachers, who put little efforts in discharging their duties, poor classroom management, lack of zeal and failure to meet set objectives of learning are said to be ineffective. In this study, indicators of teachers' job effectiveness are their devotion to discharging their duties which is evident in the performance of students in examinations and competitions.

There had been remarkable improvement on teachers' job effectiveness which is reflected in outstanding of academic achievement in examination among students in secondary schools in Anambra State (Egboka&Olisah, 2020). Adimike (2022) noted that Anambra State emerged champion in 2022 National Interschool Presidential Debate and represented Nigeria at the World Debate Championship in Vietnam in 2023 and came out victorious Also, Ovet (2023) reported that a team of students from Anambra State clinched second place in World Affairs Challenge global competition 2023 in United States. inAnambra State have continued to celebrate national education dominance, the latest being that the students with the highest score in 2023 JAMB examination came from the state. The excellence performance recorded by secondary school students in external examinations and competitions within and outside the country which has continued to attract more laurels to Anambra State could probably be attributed the principals' utilization of committee system in motivating the teachers to put substantial efforts in discharging their duties irrespective of their gender.

Gender is the behaviour, cultural role and social expectations that are associated to being males and females. Udemé and Chibuzor (2023) defined gender as the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between masculine and feminine (males and females). The societal expectations of gender tend to influence the manner in which male and female teachers perform their instructional roles in the schools to improve their job effectiveness. Eccles cited in Dicke, Safavian and Eccles (2019) noted that the general beliefs about responsibilities and behaviours deemed appropriate for males and females influence their work attitudes. Thus, gender may influence roles and behaviours of teachers which have bearing on their job effectiveness. Researches undertaken on the basis of gender-related differences in teachers' job effectiveness yielded inconsistent results. For instance, Sharma (2022) revealed that male and female elementary school teachers differ significantly in their teacher effectiveness. Also, Dien, Abang and Ngban (2022) reported that female teachers are more effective in their job than their male counterparts in secondary schools. On the contrary, Pathak and Deepshikha (2020) revealed that no significant difference was found between the job effectiveness of male and female teachers in secondary schools. In the same vein, Choudhary and Arora (2015) revealed no significant difference exists in mean scores of job effectiveness of male and female teachers at secondary level. The possible explanation for these controversial findings might be probably because the studies were carried out with different organizations and society with different gender roles and expectations. The need arises for further studies to take gender into consideration to investigate principals' utilization of committee system as predictors of teachers' job effectiveness.

Statement of the Problem

Anambra State has consistently emerged among the overall states in the performance ranking charts of West African Senior School Certificate Examination over some decades. Also, the results of students from Anambra State have continued to remain among the top best in the examinations conducted by Joint Admission and Matriculation Board. Remarkably, some secondary school students in Anambra State have been celebrated for outstanding performance in national and international

competitions. The job effectiveness of the teachers might have contributed in preparing secondary school students to excel in these examinations and competitions.

The job effectiveness of teachers could be traced to the support; motivation and guidance received from the principals to engage in best teaching practices. The practices of principals in constituting committees in secondary schools could encourage diverse opinions and rendering of support required by teachers to prepare students for examinations and competitions. Premised on this problem, the study therefore investigated principals' utilization of committee system and instructional leadership practices as predictors of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the principals' utilization of committee system as predictors of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. Principals' utilization of committee system as a predictor of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' utilization of committee system as a predictor of male teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Principals' utilization of committee system as a predictor of female teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does principals' utilization of committee system predicts teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. How does principals' utilization of committee system predicts male teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. How does principals' utilization of committee system predicts female teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Principals' utilization of committee system is not a significant predictor of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' utilization of committee system is not a significant predictor of male teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Principals' utilization of committee system is not a significant predictor of female teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The study was conducted in Anambra State which is one of the five states in South-Eastern Nigeria. The choice of Anambra State for the study is informed by remarkable academic achievement of students which could be attributed to teachers' job effectiveness might be associated with the principals' utilization of committee system. The population of the study comprised 5,286 teachers (1,872 males and 3,124 females) in the 263 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample size for this study consisted of 529 teachers (187 males and 342 females) representing 10 percent of the population was drawn using drawn using proportionate stratified sampling technique. The 10% of the population is within the recommendation

of Nwana cited in Adekeye and Apeh (2019) who opined that if the population is a few hundreds, a 40% or more sample will do; if many hundreds, a 20% sample will do; if a few thousands, a 10% sample will do and if several thousands, a 5% or less sample will do. Since the population is in several thousands, the researchers draw 10% which can be conveniently and adequately managed .

Two sets of instruments titled “Principals’ Utilization of Committee System Questionnaire (PUCSQ)” and “Teachers’ Job Effectiveness Scale (TJES)” were used for data collection. The researcher developed the instruments from literature review and consultation of experts in the field of education. PUCSQ has two sections namely, A and B. Section “A” deals with the demographic variable of the respondents such as gender. Section B contains 34 items. TJES has two sections namely, A and B. Section “A” deals with the demographic variable of the respondents such as gender. Section B contains 22 items which measure teachers’ job effectiveness. The two sets of instruments were structured on a four-point rating of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The face validation of the instruments were determined by three experts, two in the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Department of Educational Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation Unit) all from Faculty of Education, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka. Their suggestions were used to produce the final version of the instruments used for data collection. Cronbach alpha was used to determine internal consistency of the research instruments. The These yielded co-efficient values of 0.78 for PUCSQ and 0.81 for TJES. This is in line with Said (2018) who recommended that a co-efficient (r) of 0.75 and above should be considered high enough to judge an instrument as reliable.

The researcher, with the help of five research assistants who are secondary school teachers in Anambra State, used direct approach for data collection. A total of 529 copies of instruments were distributed to (187 males and 342 females) and 518 (181 males and 337 females) copies of questionnaires were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating 98 percent return rate. The copies of the instruments distributed, properly filled and successfully were used for data analysis.

Simple regression was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses. For decision on the research questions, the coefficient r and the size of the relationship correlation was interpreted using the correlation coefficient by Alsagr (2021), as follows

Coefficient	Correlation
.00- .19	Weak correlation
.20- .39	Fair correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
-.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less ($\leq$) than significant value of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of .05 the null hypotheses was accepted.

Result

Research Question 1: How does principals’ utilization of committee system predicts teachers’ job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Principals' Utilization of Committee System as Predictor of Teachers' Job Effectiveness

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
1	.745	.555	.555	.29103	Strong

Result in table 1 revealed that the correlation coefficient of simple regression analysis between principals' utilization committee system and teachers' job effectiveness is .745 with a coefficient of determination of .555. This shows that 55.5 % variation in teachers' job effectiveness can be attributed to principals' utilization committee system. The regression Coefficient r of .745 indicated that principals' utilization of committee system is a strong predictor of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: How does principals' utilization of committee system predicts male teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Principals' Utilization of Committee System as Predictor of Male Teachers' Job Effectiveness

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
1	.682	.465	.462	.56120	Moderate

As shown in table 2, the correlation coefficient of simple regression analysis between principals' utilization committee system and male teachers' job effectiveness is .682 with a coefficient of determination of .465. This shows that 46.5 % variation in male teachers' job effectiveness can be attributed to principals' utilization committee system. The regression Coefficient r of .682 indicated that principals' utilization of committee system is a moderate predictor of male teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State

Research Question 3: How does principals' utilization of committee system predicts female teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Principals' Utilization of Committee System as Predictor of Female Teachers' Job Effectiveness

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
1	.718	.515	.7514	.44745	Strong

Result in table 3 showed that the correlation coefficient of simple regression analysis between principals' utilization committee system and female teachers' job effectiveness is .718 with a coefficient of determination of .515. This shows that 51.5 % variation in female teachers' job effectiveness can be attributed to principals' utilization committee system. The regression Coefficient r of .718 indicated that principals' utilization of committee system is a strong predictor of female teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State

Hypothesis One: Principals' utilization of committee system is not a significant predictor of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Simple Regression on Principals’ Utilization of Committee System as Significant Predictor of Teachers’ Job Effectiveness

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Committee System	.745	.555	644.594	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 4, the simple regression coefficient (R) is .745, while the R² is .555 showing that principals’ utilization of committee system makes 55.5% contribution to the variance in teachers’ job effectiveness. The *F* (1/518) =644.594 and the *p*-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the *p*-value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals’ utilization of committee system is a significant predictor of teachers’ job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two: Principals’ utilization of committee system is not a significant predictor of male teachers’ job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Simple Regression on Principals’ Utilization of Committee System as a Significant Predictor of Male Teachers’ Job Effectiveness

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Committee System	.682	.465	155.710	.000	*S

*Significant

Result in table 5 indicates that the simple regression coefficient (R) is .682, while the R² is .465 showing that principals’ utilization of committee system makes 46.5% contribution to the variance in male teachers’ job effectiveness. The *F* (1/181) =155.710 and the *p*-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the *p*-value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals’ utilization of committee system is a significant predictor of male teachers’ job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three: Principals’ utilization of committee system is not a significant predictor of female teachers’ job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Simple Regression on Principals’ Utilization of Committee System as a Significant Predictor of Female Teachers’ Job Effectiveness

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Committee System	.718	.515	356.154	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in table 6, the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.718, while the R² is 0.515 showing that principals’ utilization of committee system makes 51.5% contribution to the variance in female teachers’ job effectiveness. The *F* (1/337) =356.154 and the *p*-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the *p*-value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals’ utilization of committee system is not a significant predictor of female teachers’ job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that principals' utilization of committee system is a strong predictor of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Pindar (2021) which revealed that there was strong relationship between committee system and legislative job effectiveness. This also supported the finding of Aja-Okorie and Oko (2023) which revealed that there was a strong positive relationship between the use of university committee system and university management effectiveness. This agreement in the findings could be attributed to the fact that the studies were conducted in the same time span and country where there is similar mode use of using committee system in education institutions. This finding could be explained by the fact that committee system enhances teamwork which promotes sharing of ideas that results in better decisions and strongly improve the job effectiveness of teachers. The committee system serves as training ground for teachers to widen their knowledge and acquire skills that can strongly improve the job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. Committee system gives teachers a sense of belonging and recognition which motivate them to work hard to improve their job effectiveness. The utilization of committee system improves communication and generation of different viewpoints which lead to teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools.

It was also found that principals' utilization of committee system is a significant predictor of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. This affirmed the finding of Pindar (2021) which revealed that there was significant relationship between committee system and legislative job effectiveness. This also agreed with the finding of Aja-Okorie and Oko (2023) which indicated that there was a significant relationship between the use of university committee system and university management effectiveness. The agreement in findings could be connected to the fact that the studies were conducted in education institutions in the same country. The motivation, cooperation and commitment derived from teachers' participation in committee system might be connected to the significant relationship with their job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

The finding of the study revealed that principals' utilization of committee system is a moderate predictor of male teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. This disagreed with the finding of Zahra, Rokhmat and Baehaqi (2019) which indicated that there was positive strong relationship between the role of school committee and job effectiveness of male teachers. The difference in time span and geographical location with varied policies that influence instructional leadership practices could account for the disagreement in the findings. This finding is explained by the fact that male teachers in committee gain wider range of experience and skills that might account for the moderate relationship with their job effectiveness. There could be gender roles and expectations in committee system which shape the behaviour of male teachers and contribute to their moderate job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The principals' utilization of committee system enables male teachers makes valuable suggestions and recommendations which moderately increase their job effectiveness.

It was also found that principals' utilization of committee system is a significant predictor of male teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Zahra, Rokhmat and Baehaqi (2019) which indicated that there was significant relationship between the role of school committee and job effectiveness of male teachers. The agreement in findings could explain by the fact creative ideas which emerge from interactions among male teachers in committee. Male teachers' participation in discharging duties of committee provides opportunity

for them to learn through experience which account for the significant relationship with their job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

It was found that principals' utilization of committee system is a strong predictor of female teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in agreement with the finding of Zahra, Rokhmat and Baehaqi (2019) which indicated that there was positive strong relationship between the role of school committee and job effectiveness of female teachers. The agreement in the findings could attribute to the fact that the studies were conducted in educational institution using teachers as the participants. The finding could be explained by the fact that most female teacher are probably made members of academic committees that require less physical strengths to enable them acquire skills which might be associated with the strong prediction of their job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, the possible explanation for this finding is that committee system makes female teachers feel integral members of school which boost their morale and make them work harder to moderately improve their job effectiveness in secondary schools. Committee system which promotes the dispersion of power to female teachers makes them feel valued and they reciprocate the gesture by their commitment to duties for improve their job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

It was also revealed that principals' utilization of committee system is a significant predictor of female teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is also in line with the finding of Zahra, Rokhmat and Baehaqi (2019) which indicated that there was significant relationship between the role of school committee and job effectiveness of female teachers. The education institutions in which the studies were conducted might explain the agreement in the findings. This finding could explain by the fact that committee system provides opportunity for female teachers to widen the knowledge of means of carrying their duties to significantly improve their job effectiveness in secondary schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that principals' utilization of committee is positive and significant predictors of teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. The committee system provides forum for discussing existing problems to gain new ideas of performing tasks to improve the job effectiveness of teachers. Committee system is an effective way of delegating tasks for accomplishing a lot of jobs in secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Ministry of Education should develop policy manual for members of different committee to reference in running the affairs of schools to improve the job effectiveness of teachers.
2. Principals should ensure fairness in gender representation in composing committee system to facilitate the job effectiveness of male and female teachers.
3. Ministry of Education should organise annual professional development programme on committee system for principals to enable them upgrade their skills and knowledge of managing the activities of committee for enhancing teachers' job effectiveness.

References

- Adimike, G. (2022, November, 18th). All Hallows Seminary, Onitsha shines as Team Anambrawins National Interschool Presidential Debate. *Vanguard Nigeria*. Retrieved from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2022/11/all-hallows-seminary-onitsha-shines-as-team-anambra-wins-national-interschool-presidential-debate> on 7th November, 2023.
- Aja-Okorie, U. & Oko, N.O. (2023). University leadership through committee system as a correlates of university management effectiveness in Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria. *Journal of Education*, 9(1), 1-10.
- Arop, F.O., Owan, V.J. & Ekpang, M.A. (2018). School hazards management and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Ikom Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 4(9), 38-49.
- Choudhary, N.K. & Arora, M. (2015). Study of teacher effectiveness among male and female teachers at secondary level in Punjab. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 5(9), 327-328.
- Dicke, A., Safavian, N. & Eccles, J.E. (2019). Traditional gender roles beliefs and career attainment in STEM: A gendered story. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10(1), 1-14.
- Dien, C.A., Abang, K.B. & Ngban, A.N. (2022). Demographic factors and teachers' effectiveness among secondary school teachers in Calabar Education Zone Cross River State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 21(1), 149-157.
- Egboka, P.N. & Olisah, O.B. (2020). Relationship between principals' administrative strategies and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal for Social Studies*, 6(1), 33-41.
- Edomwande, C.I. & Anakah, D.N. (2020). Principals' leadership styles in secondary schools in Nigeria: Implications for teachers' job performance. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Educational Planning and Administration*, 5(2), 158-164.
- Jaiyeoba, A.O. & Ojewumi, M.J. (2022). Committee system and secondary school administrative effectiveness in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Educational Management*, 22(2), 251-268.
- Morrison, J., Tambahangphe, K., Sen, A., Gram, L., Budhathoki, B., Neupane, R., Thapa, K., Dahal, B., Thapa, B., Manandhar, D., Costello, A. & Osrin, D. (2020). Health management committee strengthening and community mobilization through women's groups to improve trained health worker attendance at birth in rural Nepal: A cluster randomized controlled trial. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 20(1), 1-16.
- Nnebedum, C., Oshia, E.C., Nwanne, E.I. & Chinagorom, E.C. (2022). Principals' utilization of health committee and motivational technique as predictors of managerial effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *Academic Journal of Current Research*, 9(11), 1-8.

- Nnebedum, C. Akinfolarin, A.V. &Obuegbe, A.S. (2018).Extent of principals' utilization of committee system in the administration of secondary schools.*Journal of Education &Entrepreneurship*, 5(3), 34-48.
- Nwachukwu, O.L. &Emunemu, B.O. (2021).Principal leadership style and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria.*African Journal of Educational Management*, 21(1), 71-78.
- Nwangwa, K.C.K. &Barrah, I.M. (2021). Principal-staff relationship for effective administration of secondary schools In Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.*International Journal of Innovative Development & Policy Studies*, 9 (4), 187-197.
- Ogunode, N.J. &Mcbrown, R.I. (2022). Committee system in Nigerian public tertiary institutions: Problems and way forward. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 5(5), 1-9.
- Okogbaa, V.E. &Igbogi, I. (2019).Teachers' effectiveness as a tool for students' performance in junior secondary schools in Bayelsa State.*International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, 6(4), 113-121.
- Okorji, P. &Njoku, N.E.A. (2020).Relationship between school climate and principals' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Imo State, Nigeria.*National Journal of Educational Leadership*, 5(1), 99-111.
- Onyali, L.C., Nnebedum, C. &Ejesi, N. (2020).Principals' application of total quality management practices for enhancing teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.*National Journal of Educational Leadership*, 5(2), 110-119.
- Ovet, M. (2023, May 30). Anambra students win another global competition in US. *Tribune Online*.Retrived form <http://tribuneonlinimg.com/-anambra-students-win-another-global-competition-in-us/> on 7 November.
- Pindar, D. (2021). Committee system and legislative effectiveness in Nigeria National Assembly: A study of the public account committee of the 7th Senate (2011-2015). *Unpublished Thesis Submitted to the Department of Parliamentary Administration*.University of Benin.
- Pathak, R.K. &Deepshikha, S. (2020). Comparative study of teacher effectiveness of male and female teachers at secondary level.*Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 11(4), 1304-1310.
- Sharma, S.K. (2022). Teacher effectiveness of elementary school teachers in relation to gender and job satisfaction.*Journal of Applied Research in Education*, 25(1), 106-112.
- Udeme, J.B. &Chibuzor, C. (2023). Personal variables and senior secondary school students' performance in physical education in the North West Senatorial District of AkwalbomState, Nigeria. *British International Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 1-8.
- Unachukwu, G.O. &Nwanga, S.A. (2021). Staff training and performance appraisal practices adopted by principals for teachers' retention in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.*International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 7(9), 40-51.

Zahra, F., Rokhmat, J. & Baehaqi, M. (2019). Relationship between the role of school committee and democratic leadership of principals and teachers' job effectiveness. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 7(1), 285-296.